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2 **Microencapsulation with alginate/CaCO₃: A strategy for improved phage therapy**

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30 **Abstract**

31 Bacteriophages are promising therapeutic agents that can be applied to different stages of the commercial
32 food chain. In this sense, bacteriophages can be orally administered to farm animals to protect them against
33 intestinal pathogens. However, the low pH of the stomach, the activities of bile and intestinal tract enzymes
34 limit the efficacy of the phages. This study demonstrates the utility of an alginate/CaCO₃ encapsulation
35 method suitable for bacteriophages with different morphologies and to yield encapsulation efficacies of
36 ~100%. For the first time, a cocktail of three alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated bacteriophages was administered
37 as oral therapy to commercial broilers infected with *Salmonella* under farm-like conditions. Encapsulation
38 protects the bacteriophages against their destruction by the gastric juice. Phage release from capsules
39 incubated in simulated intestinal fluid was also demonstrated, whereas encapsulation ensured sufficient
40 intestinal retention of the phages. Moreover, the small size of the capsules (124–149 μm) enables their use in
41 oral therapy and other applications in phage therapy. This study evidenced that a cocktail of the three
42 alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated bacteriophages had a greater and more durable efficacy than a cocktail of the
43 corresponding non-encapsulated phages in as therapy in broilers against *Salmonella* one of the most common
44 foodborne pathogen.

45

46 **Introduction**

47 In farm animals and in aquaculture, antibiotics have been used not only in the treatment of infections but also
48 as growth promoters. However, this intensive use of antibiotics has given rise to the emergence of resistant
49 strains of commensal and pathogenic microorganisms that are able to spread to humans, either directly
50 through the food chain or indirectly via the environmental pollution caused by farm effluents¹. The
51 European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has played an essential role in monitoring and detecting the risks
52 posed by the emergence of multi-drug resistant bacteria within the food industry². As an alternative to the
53 use of antibiotics, bacteriophages are promising therapeutic agents due to their ubiquity, high specificity,
54 replication capacity inside their host, and their ease of isolation and production. The use of bacteriophage-
55 based products in different stages of the food chain^{3,4} as well as in humans^{5,6} and animals^{4,7} via different
56 routes of administration has been investigated. However, a challenge of oral phage therapy is that the phages
57 must overcome numerous adverse conditions, including the low pH of the stomach, the activity of bile, and
58 the activities of enzymes in the digestive tract⁸⁻¹⁰ and also their short residence time in the digestive tract¹¹.
59 In addition, when used in food protection bacteriophages may interact with food components and be exposed
60 to unfavourable conditions or their stability during food processing and storage may be compromised. These
61 problems can be successfully addressed by encapsulation, which would be able to protect bacteriophages
62 under similar potentially deleterious conditions. Among the many diverse biomaterials used for phage
63 encapsulation are cellulose, liposomes, alginate, whey proteins, and gelatin, which have been applied using
64 different techniques^{12,13}. Alginate is one of the most common biomaterials used in microencapsulation,
65 including that of probiotics^{14,15} and, as recently shown, bacteriophages. The latter was achieved using
66 alginate either alone or in combination with other components, in which wet capsules ranging in size from
67 310 μm to almost 1 mm were obtained^{8,10,16-18}. Alginate, a linear copolymer containing blocks of (1,4)-
68 linked β -D-mannuronate and α -L-guluronate residues, is of low toxicity and immunogenicity and thus
69 regarded as a biocompatible material¹⁹. When used as a hydrogel in biomedical applications¹⁹, alginate is
70 combined with ionic cross-linking agents, such as divalent cations. In oral bacteriophage therapy, it protects
71 the phage by shrinking at low pH values, dissolving at high pH values⁸, and participating in mucoadhesive
72 interactions with gastrointestinal mucus²⁰. These results were obtained from *in vitro* studies that examined
73 the interactions of alginate-encapsulated bacteriophages with simulated gastric and intestinal fluids. By
74 contrast, the use of alginate-encapsulated bacteriophages in oral phage therapy has been tested in only a few

75 *in vivo* experiments involving *Salmonella* in pigs^{21,22}. To our knowledge, the present study is the first in
76 which wet bacteriophage-containing alginate/CaCO₃ microcapsules < 150 µm in size were obtained and then
77 used as oral therapy to protect broiler chickens against *Salmonella* infection, under conditions mimicking
78 those of poultry production farms. In particular, a cocktail composed by three virulent bacteriophages
79 (UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78, and UAB_Phi87) was prepared according to previous promising results of
80 phage-therapy studies^{11,23,24}.

81 **Results**

82 **Characterization of alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated phages**

83 The three bacteriophages were encapsulated separately into alginate/CaCO₃ and their properties then
84 examined. The mean size of alginate-encapsulated UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78, and UAB_Phi87 as determined
85 by laser diffraction was 124 ± 9 µm, 141 ± 16 µm, and 149 ± 6 µm, respectively (Figure 1). The
86 alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated bacteriophages were then characterized by labelling the phage and the alginate
87 with SYBR gold and DAPI, respectively. The 3D spatially superimposed SYBR-gold (green) and DAPI-
88 (blue) fluorescence intensities are shown in Figure 2. The images show that all of the phages were properly
89 encapsulated in the capsules. This was confirmed by the encapsulation yields of 98.0% ± 1.5 for UAB_Phi20,
90 99.0% ± 0.1 for UAB_Phi78, and 99.0% ± 0.7 for UAB_Phi87 (Table 1).

91 The stability of the alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated phages was determined by storing freshly encapsulated
92 phages at 4°C for 6 months and then again measuring the percentage of encapsulated phages. As shown in
93 Table 1, for cold-stored UAB_Phi20 and UAB_Phi78 there was only a slight decrease in the encapsulation
94 percentage compared to the values of freshly encapsulated phages, whereas for cold-stored encapsulated
95 UAB_Phi87 phage there was no loss of encapsulated phage. Similarly, no decrease in the encapsulation
96 percentage was observed after maintaining the alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated phages two weeks at room
97 temperature (data not shown).

98 **Stability of the encapsulated bacteriophages in simulated gastric fluid**

99 The acid stability of the alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated phages was tested by incubating them in simulated
100 gastric fluid (SGF) (pH 2.8) for 60 min. These phages proved to be much more stable under acidic conditions
101 than their non-encapsulated counterparts (Figure 3) ($p < 0.05$). Thus, titre losses of phage UAB_Phi78 and
102 phage UAB_Phi87 were 3.1 and 2.4 log₁₀ after 30 min and 2.9 and 3.5 log₁₀ after 60 min of incubation,

103 respectively. Remarkably, there was no reduction in the titre of UAB_Phi20 after 60-min incubation with
104 SGF.

105 **Encapsulated phage release by simulated intestinal fluid**

106 The kinetics of phage release from alginate/CaCO₃ capsules incubated for up to 40 min with simulated
107 intestinal fluid (SIF) was also assessed. After 20 min of incubation in SIF, the percentage of UAB_Phi20,
108 UAB_Phi78, and UAB_Phi87 release was 79.0% ± 9.1, 60.7% ± 2.4, and 95.6% ± 7.6, respectively (Figure
109 4). After 40 min, release was nearly complete for all phages (97.7% ± 18.6, 88.4% ± 7.6, and 100.0% ± 20.8,
110 respectively; Figure 4).

111 ***In vivo* retention of bacteriophage in the chicken caecum**

112 The caecal residence time of a cocktail of the three non-encapsulated and alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated
113 phages differed significantly at all three time points tested. Thus, after 2 h the encapsulated phages were
114 retained in 95.2% of the chickens and the non-encapsulated phages in 57.1% ($p < 0.05$; Figure 5). After 48
115 and 72 h the differences were still significant ($p < 0.001$): 95.2% vs. 38.1%, and 71.4% vs. 9.5%,
116 respectively (Figure 5).

117 **Bacteriophage therapy against *Salmonella* infection in broiler chickens**

118 Cocktails prepared from non-encapsulated and alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated phages differed in their long-
119 term efficacies in protecting commercial broiler chickens against *Salmonella* infection, as determined based
120 on the caecal *Salmonella* concentration (Table 2). Thus, within the first 6 days post-infection, reductions in
121 the *Salmonella* concentration in the two treated groups were nearly the same and both were significant
122 compared to the control untreated chickens ($p < 0.001$). However, on day 1 post-infection, a greater
123 reduction of *Salmonella* counts was obtained with the non-encapsulated than the encapsulated phages ($p <$
124 0.05). The reduction in the *Salmonella* concentration in chickens administered the cocktail of non-
125 encapsulated phages was significant until day 8, the first day after treatment cessation (1.5 log₁₀ reduction; p
126 < 0.05). By contrast, the protection achieved with the cocktail of alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated phages was
127 significant vs. the control from the beginning until day 15 post-infection (days 8 and 10: $p < 0.001$; day 15: p
128 < 0.05), with reductions in *Salmonella* counts on days 8, 10, and 15, of 3.6, 3.4, and 1.7 log₁₀, respectively. A
129 further comparison of the two phage treatments showed that the reduction achieved with the cocktail of
130 alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated phages was significantly greater than that obtained with the non-encapsulated
131 phages from day 8 until the end of the experiment (days 8 and 10: $p > 0.001$; day 15: $p > 0.05$; Table 2).

132 Bacteriophage concentrations remained stable throughout the experiment and were slightly higher in the non-
133 encapsulated (4.2–4.4 log₁₀ pfu /g of caecum) than in the alginate-encapsulated (3.8–3.0 log₁₀ pfu/g of
134 caecum) group from day 1 to day 10 post-infection (Table 3). However, the concentration in the caecum of
135 the non-encapsulated group was significantly greater (5.1 log₁₀ pfu /g; $p < 0.001$) than in the alginate-
136 encapsulated (0.2 log₁₀ pfu /g) on day 15.

137 **Discussion**

138 Methods allowing the stable and controlled delivery of bacteriophages are of great value in phage therapy.
139 One such method is encapsulation, which in farm animals protects orally administered bacteriophages from
140 the harsh environment of the stomach and facilitates their retention during passage through the intestinal tract
141 to ensure a successful therapeutic effect²⁴⁻²⁶. By maintaining bacteriophage stability, micro- or nano-
142 encapsulation enables not only their oral administration through feed or water but also their administration in
143 other forms, such as inhalation, thereby assuring an adequate dose of the therapeutic phage. Furthermore,
144 encapsulation can overcome other problems related to the application of bacteriophages in food industry
145 processes. The materials used in bacteriophage encapsulation have been examined in several studies^{12, 13} and
146 include alginate, alone or in combination with other materials^{8, 10, 16-18}. However, few studies have described
147 the *in vivo* use of alginate-encapsulated bacteriophages^{21, 22, 27}. Thus, our study is the first to test a cocktail of
148 three alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated virulent bacteriophages (UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78, and UAB_Phi87)¹¹,
149²³ as oral therapy in *Salmonella*-infected poultry under farm-like conditions. Phages prepared according to
150 this method were shown to be effective in protecting broilers against infection for up to 15 days.

151 The encapsulation methodology described herein allows the encapsulation of bacteriophages with different
152 morphologies, without jeopardizing infectivity. The encapsulation efficiency values obtained in this study
153 were ~99%, similar to the percentages reported by other authors^{8, 10, 16, 17, 25}. Moreover, the alginate/CaCO₃
154 encapsulated bacteriophages showed excellent stability when stored at 4°C for 6 months, with minor losses
155 determined only for UAB_Phi20 and UAB_Phi78. Also, the encapsulated phages were stable at room
156 temperature at least for two weeks, period of time that is sufficient for the administration to animals in
157 drinking water

158 Another promising feature of the alginate/CaCO₃ microcapsules was their size (124–149 μm), which was
159 almost ten times smaller than other types of capsules described in the literature^{8, 10, 16, 17, 25} and facilitated
160 their potential commercial applications. All this is the result of various systematic studies aimed at

161 optimizing the alginate concentration (1.8 %) and the posterior curing time of the capsules in the bath of
162 CaCl_2 (90 min).

163 Phages orally administered to broilers must withstand the low pH of the stomach contents of the chickens,
164 which is typically in the range of 2.1–3.6^{28,29}. Under acidic conditions, the alginate/ CaCO_3 -encapsulated
165 phages proved to be much more stable than their non-encapsulated counterparts (Figure 3) ($p < 0.05$),
166 resulting in titre losses after 60 min of incubation in SGF that were around 5 times lower for phages
167 UAB_Phi78 and UAB_Phi87. There was no loss of encapsulated UAB_Phi20. It is reported that the
168 incorporation of CaCO_3 slows the gelation rate of alginate capsules, whereas CO_3^- ions dissociated from
169 CaCO_3 diffuse into the medium and slightly increase the pH as a role of antacid, thus protecting the
170 bacteriophages^{10,19}. Our results are in accordance with those obtained by¹⁰, who also reported a good
171 protection effect on the bacteriophage K once encapsulated in a mixture of alginate/ CaCO_3 capsules of a
172 diameter of $\sim 900 \mu\text{m}$. However, in our case, this protection effect was achieved even lowering the size of the
173 capsules down to $\sim 150 \mu\text{m}$ of size.

174 Another important feature of alginate/ CaCO_3 -encapsulated bacteriophages is their release in the animal
175 intestine, where the host pathogen is located. In this study, the three phages exhibited slightly different *in*
176 *vitro* release kinetics. Thus, whereas almost a complete release of bacteriophage UAB_Phi87 was observed
177 after 20 min of incubation in SIF, UAB_Phi20 and UAB_Phi78 were released more slowly, being this
178 release completed after 40 min (Figure 4). A potential explanation of the faster release of UAB_Phi87 is that
179 this phage has a larger size than the other two phages, which could provoke the formation of alginate
180 capsules with a lower reticular or cross-linked structure and therefore, a faster release of the encapsulated
181 phages. In addition, a comparison of our release results with those of other authors is difficult, since the size
182 and composition of the microcapsules, the composition of the SIF and the incubation conditions (pH and
183 temperature) differed^{8,10,16,18}.

184 However, bacteriophage release kinetics will undoubtedly differ *in vivo*. Currently, whether phages adhere to
185 the intestinal epithelium³⁰ or their presence becomes insignificant in the absence of the bacterial host is
186 unclear^{11,31}. The mucoadhesive properties of alginate³² could prolong the presence and the effect of
187 bacteriophages used in oral phage therapy. Our *in vivo* results of residence time demonstrate that
188 alginate/ CaCO_3 encapsulation enables the significant intestinal retention of the bacteriophages even in the
189 absence of host. Thus, bacteriophages were detected in 71.4% of the chickens 72 h after oral administration

190 of a single dose of the cocktail of encapsulated bacteriophages compared to 9.5% of the chickens treated
191 with the non-encapsulated phages ($p < 0.001$). The percentage obtained with the alginate/CaCO₃ capsules
192 was better than obtained in a previous *in vivo* study of liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages²⁴, perhaps due
193 to the higher encapsulation efficiency achieved with the former.

194 The cocktail composed of the three alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated bacteriophages demonstrated long-term
195 efficacy when used in commercial broilers chickens infected with *Salmonella*, mimicking real farm
196 conditions. Colonization by *Salmonella* was effectively reduced by administering a phage cocktail
197 composed of alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated bacteriophages to the poultry 1 day prior to infection with the
198 bacterium and for an additional 7 days during treatment. Moreover, the protective effect was significantly
199 maintained for 1 week after treatment was stopped (on day 15-post infection). Differently, the non-
200 encapsulated bacteriophages quickly loosed their effect once the treatment was stopped. During the first 6
201 days post-infection, the encapsulated and non-encapsulated cocktails were of similar efficacies, with
202 maximum reductions in *Salmonella* counts of 3.1 and 2.8 log₁₀, respectively. Only on the first day of
203 treatment was the non-encapsulate cocktail significantly more effective (reduction of 2.9 vs. 1.3 log₁₀;
204 $p < 0.05$; Table 2). This may have reflected the additional time required for the encapsulated phages to
205 accumulate to an effective therapeutic concentration following their release. Then, it is likely that the phage
206 release *in vivo* would be slower than *in vitro* SIF studies. However, the effect of the non-encapsulated
207 cocktail was abolished 1 day after the cessation of treatment (day 7 post-infection) whereas the encapsulated
208 cocktail maintained its effectiveness until the end of the experiment.

209 This is the first study to report the use of alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated bacteriophages as an *in vivo* oral
210 therapy against *Salmonella* infections in poultry. While our results are similar to those achieved with
211 liposome encapsulation²⁴, preparation of the alginate/CaCO₃ capsules is simpler and provides much higher
212 encapsulation rates. Although treatment with the alginate/CaCO₃ cocktail did not remove *Salmonella* totally,
213 the concentration of *Salmonella* used in the experimental poultry infection was very high (~6 log₁₀/g of
214 caecum). Further studies should seek to ascertain the threshold *Salmonella* concentration in poultry farming
215 and if the encapsulated cocktail could eliminate *Salmonella* from the chickens completely in those conditions.

216 Another important aspect in the success of phage therapy is the relationship between the phages and their
217 bacterial hosts. According to the literature on bacteriophage-bacterial dynamics *in vitro*, the number of phage
218 increases only when the cell density is sufficient, so that the probability of an encounter between the

219 bacteriophages and the bacteria and the subsequent infection of the latter exceeds the probability of phage
220 death³³. Therefore, the success of phage therapy is largely determined by the relationship between the
221 concentration of the bacteriophages and that of their bacterial host³⁴. However, the *in vivo* dynamics are
222 presumably much more complex because multiple external factors (e.g., rapid clearance of the
223 bacteriophages by passive/active host immunity, spatial refuges, and intestinal mucous) influence treatment
224 success³⁵.

225 In our *in vivo* study, the dynamics of the non-encapsulated and encapsulated bacteriophages in controlling
226 *Salmonella* differed which agree with a previous study performed by us with liposome-encapsulated
227 bacteriophages²⁴. Thus, with the daily administration of non-encapsulated bacteriophages, their uptake
228 together with the new phage progeny produced in the intestinal tract led to a marked decrease in the
229 *Salmonella* concentration (~50%) 1 day post-infection. Thereafter, until almost day 8 post-infection, the
230 *Salmonella* concentration increased slightly but with significant therapeutic effect. Once the phage uptake
231 was stopped, the equilibrium between phages and bacteria was disrupted and the *Salmonella* concentration
232 increased significantly with respect to day 1 post-infection (days 8 and 10, $p<0.05$; day 15 post-infection,
233 $p<0.001$; Table 2). The requirement for continuous administration of bacteriophages along the time to
234 achieve a low population of *Samonella* has also been suggested by other authors^{11,36}. Several factors as
235 partial emergence of bacteriophage-resistant *Salmonella*, bacterial phenotypic changes, physical refuges or
236 slow growth rate of bacterial cells could explain this fact^{35,36}. By contrast, when the encapsulated
237 bacteriophage cocktail was administered, the *Salmonella* concentration decreased gradually during all the
238 experiment, regardless of whether treatment was ongoing or had stopped. Therefore, the encapsulation of
239 bacteriophages abolished the need for a continuous treatment to achieve a low bacterial concentration. In this
240 case, the mucoadhesiveness of the capsules and the release kinetics of the bacteriophages from them must be
241 the most important features for this effect. It is remarkable that when the bacteriophage uptake was stopped
242 the bacteriophage concentration remained nearly constant (Table 3) in both treatments, but the *Salmonella*
243 concentration in the gut was higher in the non-encapsulated bacteriophage treatment than in encapsulated
244 one. At this respect, it has been proposed that there is a threshold density of bacteria that must be present in
245 order for the bacteriophage concentration to increase³³. Further works are needed to identify the *in vivo*
246 mechanism(s) underlying this fact.

247 In summary, this study demonstrated the utility of a simple, efficient, and inexpensive encapsulation method
248 that can be used with bacteriophages of different morphologies. The small size of the resulting microcapsules
249 (124–149 μm) enables their use in diverse applications in phage therapy. Moreover, alginate/ CaCO_3
250 encapsulation confers excellent protection against the deleterious effects of gastric juice and promotes
251 greater intestinal retention of the bacteriophages. The results presented here, together with those from our
252 previous investigation of liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages²⁴, show that encapsulation is important for a
253 prolonged and successful oral phage therapy in commercial broilers infected with *Salmonella*.

254 **Methods**

255 **Bacterial strains and growth conditions**

256 Phages UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78, and UAB_Phi87 were previously obtained by us from chicken and pig
257 farms^{11,23}. All three bacteriophages belong to the *Caudovirales* order. UAB_Phi20 and UAB_Phi78
258 bacteriophages are members of the *Podoviridae* family with icosahedral heads (60 ± 1.5 nm and 66 ± 1.7 ,
259 respectively) and short tails (13-14 nm) whereas UAB_Phi87 has also an icosahedral head (68 ± 2.7 nm) but
260 a long contractile tail (114 ± 4.3 nm) and derives from the *Myoviridae* family¹¹. The genomic features of the
261 three bacteriophages have been recently published³⁷. The bacteriophages were propagated in *Salmonella*
262 Typhimurium LB5000 (SGSC181; University of Calgary). Broiler chickens were colonized with *S.*
263 Typhimurium ATCC 14028 Rif^R. All bacterial strains were grown in Luria-Bertani (LB) broth or on LB agar
264 plates for 18 h at 37°C. *S.* Typhimurium ATCC 14028 Rif^R viable counts were obtained after incubating the
265 bacterium, plated on xylose-lysine-deoxycholate (XLD) plates (Laboratorios Conda, Spain) supplemented
266 with rifampin (75 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), at 37°C for 18 h.

267 ***In vitro* multiplication of bacteriophages**

268 High-titer (1×10^{11} – 1×10^{12} pfu/ml in 10 mM MgSO_4) lysates were obtained from bacteriophages
269 propagated in *S.* Typhimurium strain LB5000 (SGSC181; University of Calgary) and subjected to
270 ultracentrifugation at $51,000 \times g$ for 2 h (OptimaTM L-80; Beckman, CA, USA), as previously described²⁴.
271 The phage titre was determined by plating serial dilutions (1:10) onto LB plates using the double agar layer
272 method³⁸.

273 **Bacteriophage encapsulation with alginate/ CaCO_3**

274 Encapsulation of the phages using alginate/ CaCO_3 was carried out followed a previously described protocol
275 with slight modifications¹⁰. Briefly, 500 mg of CaCO_3 (1%) and 900 mg of alginate (1.8%) were added to 50

276 ml of each bacteriophage suspension in 10 mM MgSO₄ at a concentration of 1×10^{11} pfu/ml. This mixture
277 was stirred overnight to allow its proper homogenization and then pumped at a rate of 1.5 ml/min into a bath
278 containing 150 ml of 1.8% CaCl₂ using the ViscoMist™ Air Atomizing spray nozzle (inner diameter: 381
279 μm; Lechler Inc., St. Charles, IL) under a continuous flow of nitrogen at a pressure of 3 bars. The gelled
280 capsules were left to harden in the bath for 90 min with slow stirring and then centrifuged at $469 \times g$ for 5
281 min. The resulting pellet was washed thrice with 10 mM MgSO₄ and resuspended in 10 mM MgSO₄ at a
282 final volume of 50 ml.

283 Particle size distributions were determined by granulometric assays based on laser diffraction (Mastersizer
284 2000, Malvern Instruments, UK), which was appropriate because of the micrometric size of the encapsulated
285 phages. The undiluted capsules were measured directly after encapsulation; determination of their mean
286 diameter was based on three different measurements and it was expressed according to the particle size
287 analyzer protocols (Mastersizer, Malvern Instruments) in terms of the “volume weighted mean”, as the

288 $D[4,3] = \frac{\sum d^4}{\sum d^3}$, where the diameter (d) has d^4 dependence and the number of particles is not inherent in the
289 formulae.

290 The encapsulation efficiency (EE) of the phages was calculated as $EE (\%) = 100 - (C_{\text{free}}/C_{\text{total}}) \times 100$, where
291 C_{total} is the concentration of all bacteriophages and C_{free} the concentration of free phages²⁴. To determine
292 C_{total} , the product of the phage encapsulation was titrated directly. Because divalent ions are essential for the
293 stability of the alginate capsules, degradation of the plated capsules may occur due to the sequestration of
294 divalent ions during gelling of the double agar layer. To quantify C_{free} , 0.5 ml of the encapsulation product
295 was filtered through a 0.22-μm PES filter syringe to retain the encapsulated phages. The eluted volume was
296 then titered. The stability of the alginate-encapsulated phages at 4°C was tested for 6 months using the
297 above-described method for EE determination.

298 **Microscopy**

299 The phages were labeled with SYBR gold (Molecular Probes, OR, USA) as previously described²⁴, and
300 encapsulated as described above, but with the addition of 4',6-diamidino-2'-phenylindole dihydrochloride
301 (DAPI)-labeled alginate to the mixture to a final volume of 10%. Alginate labeling was performed as
302 previously described, but using DAPI rather than fluoresceinamine³⁹. Samples of 30 μl were observed using

303 a Leica TCS SP5 confocal microscope (Leica Microsystems, Germany) but without the resonance scanning
304 mode, as the capsules were large enough to reduce Brownian motion.

305 **Bacteriophage stability in simulated gastric fluid**

306 The stability of the encapsulated phages in SGF (pH 2.8), consisting of 3 mg pepsin (Sigma-Aldrich, MO,
307 USA)/ml in 0.85% NaCl, was tested as previously described²⁴. However, in this study, the solution exhibited
308 a buffering effect till a pH value of 3.8. The bacteriophage titer was determined as described above using
309 aliquots taken at 0, 30, and 60 min of incubation in SGF.

310 **Alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated phage release in simulated intestinal fluid**

311 Phage release from alginate capsules in SIF (pH 8.0), consisting of 1 mg pancreatin (Sigma-Aldrich, MO,
312 USA)/ml, 10 mM bile salts, and 0.85% NaCl⁴⁰, was determined. Thus, a suspension of alginate-encapsulated
313 phages at a concentration of 1×10^9 pfu/ml was inoculated in SIF and incubated in a water bath at 42°C with
314 agitation to emulate the conditions of the avian intestine. C_{total} and C_{free} were calculated as described above.

315 ***In vivo* assays in broilers**

316 Both the residence time in the chicken intestine and the effectiveness of a cocktail of alginate-encapsulated
317 or non-encapsulated phages against *Salmonella* was evaluated *in vivo* in commercial broilers (*Gallus gallus*,
318 Ross strain 308; Terra-Avant S.A., Girona, Spain), using an experimental model that mimics farm conditions,
319 as described in a previous study²⁴. The animals were treated in compliance with the guidelines of the
320 Comissió d'Ètica en l'Experimentació Animal i Humana (CEEAH) of the Universitat Autònoma de
321 Barcelona (UAB). The study was approved and assigned the authorization number 1953.

322 Caecum samples were collected from two euthanized chickens and tested using previously described
323 enrichment protocols²⁴, to confirm that they were free of *Salmonella* and phages.

324 A curved oral-dosing needle was used to orally administer the broilers 100 µl of a cocktail containing either
325 the alginate-encapsulated or non-encapsulated phages²⁴. The cocktail consisted of a 1:1:1 mixture of the
326 three phages (UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78, and UAB_Phi87) at a concentration of 10^{11} pfu/ml in MgSO₄ buffer
327 without antacid.

328 **Bacteriophage retention in the chicken caecum**

329 The intestinal residence time of the cocktail of either the encapsulated or non-encapsulated phages was
330 determined over 72 h. Two independent experiments were conducted with two groups of 63 1-day-old
331 chickens. The phage cocktail was administered at a dose of 10^{10} pfu/animal as described previously²⁴. After

332 2, 48, and 72 h, caecum samples were collected from 21 euthanized animals and processed as previously
333 described²⁴. The total phage number in the homogenized caecum samples was determined as described
334 above. When direct detection of the phages was not possible, an enrichment procedure was carried out using
335 a previously described method²⁴.

336 **Bacteriophage therapy**

337 Bacteriophage therapy against *Salmonella* was evaluated over 17 days in chickens orally administered the
338 different phage cocktails, as described in a previous work²⁴. Briefly, the animals were orally infected on day
339 0 with a suspension of *S. Typhimurium* ATCC14028 Rif^R (10^7 cfu/animal). Three sequential experiments
340 with groups of 84 commercial broilers (*Gallus gallus*, Ross strain 308) each were conducted. Group 1
341 corresponded to the *Salmonella* colonization control. Groups 2 and 3 received the non-encapsulated and
342 alginate-encapsulated phages, respectively. In all cases, the oral dose of the three-phage cocktail (10^{10}
343 pfu/animal) was administered once daily for 9 days (from day -1 to day 7 after *Salmonella* infection). The
344 control group was orally inoculated with MgSO₄ (10 mM). To quantify the *Salmonella* and the phages, 14
345 chickens per group were euthanized on days 1, 3, 6, 8, 10, and 15 post-infection. Sample processing and
346 determination of the *Salmonella* concentration in caecum samples were done as previously described²⁴. The
347 total concentration of bacteriophages was determined as described above. The reduction in the number of
348 bacteria in each treatment was calculated by subtracting the mean caecal concentration (expressed in log₁₀
349 units) in groups 2 and 3 from the mean value of the control (group 1).

350 **Statistical analysis**

351 All results were analyzed using IBM SPSS software. For normally distributed samples, an analysis of
352 variance (ANOVA) and Student's t test were applied; in cases of a non-normal distribution, the Kruskal-
353 Wallis and Mann-Whitney tests were used.

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365 **AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS**

366 JC and MC-S carried out the encapsulation of the bacteriophages. Moreover, JC and JO performed the *in*
367 *vivo* experiments. JA-S contributed in the encapsulation experiments. PC, MC-S, DM and ML participated in
368 the design and coordination of the study and in drafting the manuscript. All authors read and approved the
369 final version of the manuscript

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371 **COMPETING FINANCIAL INTERESTS**

372 Pilar Cortés and Montserrat Llagostera are the inventors of the patent application EP2750519.

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384 **References**

- 385 1. Liebana, E. et al. Public health risks of enterobacterial isolates producing extended-spectrum beta-
386 lactamases or AmpC beta-lactamases in food and food-producing animals: an EU perspective of
387 epidemiology, analytical methods, risk factors, and control options. *Clin. Infect. Dis.* **56**, 1030–1037,
388 doi: 10.1093/cid/cis1043 (2013).
- 389 2. European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), European Food Safety Authority (EFSA),
390 European Medicines Agency (EMA). Joint opinion on antimicrobial resistance (AMR) focused on
391 zoonotic infections. *EFSA Journal* **7(11)**, 1372, doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2009.1372 (2009).
- 392 3. Sillankorva, S.M., Oliveira, H. & Azeredo, J. Bacteriophages and their role in food safety. *Int. J.*
393 *Microbiol.* **2012**: 863945, doi: 10.1155/2012/863945 (2012).
- 394 4. Endersen, L., O'Mahony, J., Hill, C., Ross, P., McAuliffe, O. & Coffey, A. Phage therapy in the food
395 industry. *Annu. Rev. Food Sci. Technol.* **5**, 327-349, doi: 10.1146/annurev-food-030713-092415 (2014).
- 396 5. Abedon, S.T., Kuhl, S.J., Blasdel, B.G. & Kutter, E.M. Phage treatment of human infections.
397 *Bacteriophage* **1:2**, 66-85, doi: 10.4161/bact.1.2.15845 (2011).
- 398 6. Vandenheuvel, D., Lavigne, R., & Brüßow, H.. Bacteriophage Therapy: advances in formulation
399 strategies and human clinical trials. *Annu. Rev. Virol.* **2**, 599-618, doi: 10.1146/annurev-virology-
400 100114-054915 (2015).
- 401 7. Ryan, E.M., Gorman, S.P., Donnelly, R.F. & Gilmore, B.F. Recent advances in bacteriophage therapy:
402 how delivery routes, formulation, concentration and timing influence the success of phage therapy. *J.*
403 *Pharm. Pharmacol.* **63**, 1253–1264, doi: 10.1111/j.2042-7158.2011.01324.x. (2011).
- 404 8. Ma, Y et al. Microencapsulation of bacteriophage Felix O1 into chitosan-alginate microspheres for oral
405 delivery. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **74**, 4799–4805, doi: 10.1128/AEM.00246-08 (2008).
- 406 9. Wang, Q. & Sabour, P.M. Encapsulation and controlled release of bacteriophages for food animal
407 production. In *Bacteriophages In The Control Of Food- And Waterbone Pathogens.* (eds Parviz M
408 Sabour, P.M. & Mansel W Griffiths, M.W.) (ASM Press, Washington, DC, 2010).
- 409 10. Ma, Y., Pacan, J.C., Wang, Q., Sabour, P.M., Huang, X. & Xu, Y. Enhanced alginate microspheres as
410 means of oral delivery of bacteriophage for reducing *Staphylococcus aureus* intestinal carriage. *Food*
411 *Hydrocoll.* **26**, 434–440, doi: 10.1016/j.foodhyd.2010.11.017 (2012).

- 412 11. Bardina, C., Spricigo, D.A., Cortés, P. & Llagostera, M. Significance of the bacteriophage treatment
413 schedule in reducing *Salmonella* colonization of poultry. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **78**, 6600–6607, doi:
414 10.1128/AEM.01257-12 (2012).
- 415 12. Choinska-Pulit, A., Mituła, P., Sliwka, P., Łaba, W. & Skaradzinska, A. Bacteriophage encapsulation:
416 trends and potential applications. *Trends Food Sci. Tech.* **45**, 212e221, doi: 10.1016/j.tifs.2015.07.001
417 (2015).
- 418 13. Hussain, M.A., Liu, H., Wang Q, Zhong F., Guo, Q. & Balamurugan, S. Use of encapsulated
419 bacteriophages to enhance farm to fork food safety. *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* **11**, 0, doi:
420 10.1080/10408398.2015.1069729 (2015).
- 421 14. Kailasapathy, K. Microencapsulation of probiotic bacteria: technology and potential applications. *Curr.*
422 *Issues Intest. Microbiol.* **3**, 39-48 (2002).
- 423 15. D’Orazio, G. et al. Microencapsulation of new probiotic formulations for gastrointestinal delivery: in
424 vitro study of assess viability and biological properties. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **99**, 9779-9789, doi:
425 10.1007/s00253-015-6853-1 (2015).
- 426 16. Tang, Z., Huang, X., Baxi, S., Chambers, J.R., Sabour, P.M. & Wang, Q. Whey protein improves
427 survival and release characteristics of bacteriophage FelixO1 encapsulated in alginate microspheres.
428 *Food Res. Int.* **52**, 460-466, doi: 10.1016/j.foodres.2012.12.037 (2013).
- 429 17. Tang, Z., Huang, X., Sabour, P.M., Chambers, J.R. & Wang, Q. Preparation and characterization of dry
430 powder bacteriophage K for intestinal delivery through oral administration. *LWT-Food Sci. Technol.* **60**,
431 263-270, doi: 10.1016/j.lwt.2014.08.012 (2015).
- 432 18. Samtlebe, M et al. Carrier systems for bacteriophages to supplement food systems: Encapsulation and
433 controlled release to modulate the human gut microbiota. *LWT - Food Sci. Technol.* **68**, 334-340, doi:
434 10.1016/j.lwt.2015.12.039 (2016).
- 435 19. Lee K.Y. & Mooney D.J. Alginate: properties and biomedical applications. *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **37**(1), 106-
436 126, doi: 10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2011.06.003 (2012).
- 437 20. Sosnik, A. Alginate particles as platform for drug delivery by the oral route: state-of-the-art. *ISRN*
438 *Pharm.* **2014**, 926157, doi: 10.1155/2014/926157 (2014).

- 439 21. Wall, S.K., Zhang, J., Rostagno, M.H. & Ebner, P.D. Phage therapy to reduce preprocessing *Salmonella*
440 infections in market-weight swine. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **76**, 48-53, doi: 10.1128/AEM.00785-09
441 (2010).
- 442 22. Saez, A.C., Zhang, J., Rostagno, M.H. & Ebner, P.D. Direct feeding of microencapsulated bacteriophages
443 to reduce *Salmonella* colonization in pigs. *Foodborne Pathog. Dis.* **8**, 1269-1274, doi:
444 10.1089/fpd.2011.0905 (2011).
- 445 23. Spricigo, D.A., Bardina, C., Cortés, P. & Llagostera, M. Use of a bacteriophage cocktail to control
446 *Salmonella* in food and the food industry. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* **165**, 169–174, doi:
447 10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2013.05.009 (2013).
- 448 24. Colom, J., Cano-Sanabria, M., Otero, J., Cortés, P., Maspoch, D. & Llagostera, M. L Liposome-
449 encapsulated bacteriophages for enhanced oral phage therapy against *Salmonella* spp. *Appl. Environ.*
450 *Microbiol.* **81**, 4841-4849, doi: 10.1128/AEM.00812-15 (2015).
- 451 25. Dini, C., Islan, G.A., de Urza, P.J. & Castro, G.R. Novel biopolymer matrices for Microencapsulation
452 of phages: enhanced protection against acidity and protease activity. *Macromol Biosci* **12**, 1200–1208,
453 doi: 10.1002/mabi.201200109 (2012).
- 454 26. Dini, C., Islan, G.A. & Castro, G.R. Characterization and stability analysis of biopolymeric matrices
455 designed for phage-controlled release. *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.* **174**, 2031–2047, doi:
456 10.1007/s12010-014-1152-3 (2014).
- 457 27. Stanford, K et al. Oral delivery systems for encapsulated bacteriophages targeted at *Escherichia coli*
458 O157:H7 in feedlot cattle. *J. Food Prot.* **7**, 1304-1312 (2010).
- 459 28. Jiménez-Moreno, E., González-Alvarado, J.M., González-Sánchez, D., Lázaro, R. & Mateos, G.G.
460 Effects of type and particle size of dietary fiber on growth performance and digestive traits of broilers
461 from 1 to 21 days of age. *Poult. Sci.* **89**, 2197-2212, doi: 10.3382/ps.2010-00771. (2010).
- 462 29. Sacranie, A., Svihus, B., Denstadli, V., Moen, B., Iji, P.A. & Choct, M. The effect of insoluble fiber and
463 intermittent feeding on gizzard development, gut motility and performance of broiler chickens. *Poult. Sci.*
464 **91**, 693-700, doi: 10.3382/ps.2011-01790 (2012).
- 465 30. Barr, J.J., et al. Bacteriophage adhering to mucus provide a non-host-derived immunity. *Proc. Natl. Acad.*
466 *Sci. USA* **110**, 10771–1776, doi: 10.1073/pnas.1305923110 (2013).

- 467 31. Atterbury, R.J. et al. Bacteriophage therapy to reduce *Salmonella* colonization of broiler chickens. *Appl.*
468 *Environ. Microbiol.* **73**, 4543–4549, doi: 10.1128/AEM.00049-07 (2007).
- 469 32. George, M. & Abraham, T.E. Polyionic hydrocolloids for the intestinal delivery of protein drugs:
470 Alginate and chitosan -a review. *J. Control Release* **114**, 1–14, doi: 10.1016/j.jconrel.2006.04.017 (2006).
- 471 33. Payne, R.J. & Jansen, V.A. Understanding bacteriophage therapy as a density-dependent kinetic process.
472 *J. Theor. Biol.* **208**, 37-48, doi: 10.1006/jtbi.2000.2198 (2001).
- 473 34. Payne, R.J. & Jansen, V.A. Pharmacokinetic principles of bacteriophage therapy. *Clin. Pharmacokinet.*
474 **42**, 315-325, doi: 10.2165/00003088-200342040-00002 (2003).
- 475 35. Bull, J.J. & Gill, J.J. The habits of highly effective phages: population dynamics as a framework for
476 identifying therapeutic phages. *Front. Microbiol.* **5**, 618, doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2014.00618 (2014).
- 477 36. Hurley, A., Maurer, J.J. & Lee M.D. Using bacteriophages to modulate *Salmonella* colonization of the
478 chicken's gastrointestinal tract: Lessons learned from *in silico* and *in vivo* modelling. *Avian Dis.* **52**, 599-
479 607, doi: 10.1637/8288-031808-reg.1 (2008).
- 480 37. Bardina, C., Colom, J., Spricigo, D.A., Otero, J., Sánchez-Osuna, M., Cortés, P. & Llagostera, M.
481 Genetics and genomics of three new bacteriophages useful in the biocontrol of *Salmonella*. *Front.*
482 *Microbiol.* **7**, 545, doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2016.00545 (2016).
- 483 38. Green, M.R. & Sambrook, J. In *Molecular Cloning: A Laboratory Manual*, 4rd ed. (Cold Spring Harbor
484 Laboratory Press, 2012).
- 485 39. Hadjialirezaei, S. *Coating Of Alginate Capsules*. PhD Thesis. Norwegian University of Science and
486 Technology (2013).
- 487 40. Musikasang, H., Tani, A., H-Kittikun, A. & Maneerat S. Probiotic potential of lactic acid bacteria
488 isolated from chicken gastrointestinal digestive tract. *World J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **25**, 1337–1345, doi:
489 10.1007/s11274-009-0020-8 (2009).

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492 **Figure Legends**

493 **Figure 1.** Characterization of the alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated bacteriophages. Particle size distribution
494 plots of the alginate-encapsulated bacteriophages UAB_Phi20 (a), UAB_Phi78 (b), and UAB_Phi87 (c) were
495 obtained by laser diffraction.

496 **Figure 2.** 3D confocal microscopy images of SYBR-gold-labelled UAB_Phi20 (a), UAB_Phi78 (b), and
497 UAB_Phi87 (c) (green) encapsulated in DAPI-labelled alginate capsules (blue). 3D images of the capsules
498 are shown on the left (1), and the corresponding cross-sectional images in the middle (2) and on the right (3).
499 Scale bars, 30 µm.

500 **Figure 3.** Stability of the non-encapsulated (light gray bars) and alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated (dark gray
501 bars) bacteriophages in simulated gastric fluid. (a) UAB_Phi20, (b) UAB_Phi78, and (c) UAB_Phi87. Each
502 value is the average of six independent experiments ± standard deviation. * $p < 0.05$.

503 **Figure 4.** *In vitro* release of alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated UAB_Phi20 (○), UAB_Phi78 (■), and
504 UAB_Phi87 (◇) incubated in simulated intestinal fluid. Each value is the average of three independent
505 experiments ± standard deviation.

506 **Figure 5.** Persistence of the non-encapsulated (light gray) and alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated (dark gray)
507 bacteriophages in the broiler caecum. * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$.

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509 **Table 1.** Percentage (%) of alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated phages after their storage at 4°C for 6 months.

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Bacteriophage	Fresh ^a	Stored at 4°C ^a	
		Three months	Six months
UAB_Phi20	98.0 ± 1.5	84.0 ± 0.7	74.0 ± 8.6
UAB_Phi78	99.0 ± 0.1	89.0 ± 2.3	73.0 ± 4.2
UAB_Phi87	99.0 ± 0.7	92.0 ± 5.9	94.0 ± 5.2

^a Each value represents the average from three independent experiments ± standard deviation.

518 **Table 2.** *Salmonella* concentration in the caeca of broilers treated with alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated and
 519 non-encapsulated bacteriophages.

Day post-infection	<i>Salmonella</i> concentration in caecum (log ₁₀ cfu/g) ^a		
	Control group	Encapsulated group	Non-encapsulated group
1	5.8 ± 0.7	4.5 ± 1.4 ^b	2.9 ± 2.3 ^{b,c}
3	6.6 ± 0.5	4.0 ± 1.5 ^b	3.3 ± 2.7 ^b
6	6.9 ± 0.8	3.8 ± 2.2 ^b	4.1 ± 2.1 ^b
8	6.7 ± 0.5	3.1 ± 2.5 ^{b,c}	5.2 ± 2.2 ^{b,d}
10	6.4 ± 1.0	3.0 ± 0.9 ^{b,c}	5.7 ± 1.9 ^d
15	5.2 ± 1.3	3.5 ± 2.1 ^{b,c}	6.3 ± 1.0 ^d

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521 ^a Each value is the average from 14 caecum samples ± standard deviation.

522 ^b Statistical significance between the control and each treated group ($p < 0.001$ at days 1 to 6; for $p < 0.001$ at
 523 days 8 and 10 for the encapsulated group, and $p < 0.05$ at day 8 for non-encapsulated group and at day 15 for
 524 encapsulated group).

525 ^c Statistical significance between the two treated groups $p < 0.05$ at days 1 and 8, and $p < 0.001$ on days 10
 526 and 15.

527 ^d Statistical significance of the increase of *Salmonella* concentration at days 8 and 10 ($p < 0.05$), and on day
 528 15 ($p < 0.001$), with respect day 1 post-infection.

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537 **Table 3.** Bacteriophage concentrations in the caeca of broilers treated with alginate/CaCO₃-encapsulated and
538 non-encapsulated bacteriophages.

Days post-infection	Bacteriophage concentration in caecum (log ₁₀ pfu/g) ^a	
	Encapsulated group	Non-encapsulated group
1	3.8 ± 1.0	4.2 ± 0.6
3	3.5 ± 1.0	4.7 ± 1.7
6	3.6 ± 1.4	4.0 ± 0.8
8	3.8 ± 1.2	4.2 ± 2.1
10	3.0 ± 1.7	4.4 ± 2.7
15	0.2 ± 0.6	5.1 ± 2.2 ^b

539 ^a Each value is the average from 14 caecum samples ± standard deviation.

540 ^b Statistical significance between the encapsulated and non-encapsulated groups ($p < 0.001$).

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1**2****3****a**

